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SYNTHESIS OF ORGANOSILICON POLYMER BASED ON HYDROLYZED POLYACRYLONITRILE

Dr. Firuz F. Rakhimov

Phd., Associate Professor Department Of Technology Of Building Materials And
Structures, Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute, Uzbekistan

Sabria I. Ibodova

Master Student, Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute, Uzbekistan

Gulhayo K. Kholikova

Master Student, Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: The article presents the synthesis of organosilicon compounds based on tetraethoxylane and industrial by-products, and also studied the ratio of reagents, solvents and temperature to the reaction product. Hydrophobic compositions based on synthesized organosilicon polymers were also developed and tests of the building material - concrete were carried out.

KEYWORDS: Hypane, acrylic emulsion, liquid glass, hydrophobization, reaction efficiency, concrete, hydrophobic compositions.

INTRODUCTION

The world pays great attention to the production of moisture protection products based on modern technologies and their use to increase the moisture resistance of building materials and structures. The creation of chemical materials that increase hydrophobicity and their inclusion in the composition of building materials is an urgent problem in all respects. Therefore, it is important to create a new generation of complex chemicals based on innovative technologies in the creation of moisture-resistant hydrophobic materials and their use in various fields.

At this time, organosilicon compounds are widely used to protect building materials from aggressive environmental influences. This is due to the fact that organosilicon compounds have the property of film formation and the film, in turn, being part of the processed material,

consists of alternating silicon and oxygen atoms. In addition, organosilicon compounds, on the one hand, bind to the workpiece through an oxygen bridge, and on the other hand, reduce the wetting of the object due to the presence of nonpolar molecular alkyl or aryl radicals[1,3,4].

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In connection with the above, tetraethoxysilane and secondary industrial raw materials were used for the synthesis of new types of polymer compounds, the creation of new hydrophobic compositions, the production of hydrophobic building materials and the expansion of the range of the most widely used organosilicon compounds.

Hydrolyzed polyacrylonitrile, which is a secondary industrial raw material, is obtained by hydrolysis of acrylonitrile. The number of functional groups may vary depending on the reaction conditions (temperature, type of catalyst, presence of organic solvent) [6,8,9].

The structure of HYPANE and its functional groups is described below:

a, b, c, x depend on the conditions and duration of the hydrolysis reaction.

The binder tetraethoxysilane (Si (C₂H₅O)₄) was used for the synthesis of a hydrophobic substance in the reactor⁴) and industrial secondary raw materials HYPANE in a ratio of 1:10 and at a temperature of 40 oC.

With an increase in temperature and the amount of TEOS, the solid mass obtained as a result of large-scale crosslinking becomes insoluble in solvents, which is probably due to the complete crosslinking of the reagents. The linear form of HYPANE is explained by the fact that the solubility of the resulting polymer decreases with an increase in the degree of transition to the lattice state and the formation of a solid mass[5].

The reaction of functional groups of hydrolyzed polyacrylonitrile with tetraethoxysilane based on experiments is described below:

In diagram b (the number of functional groups in the schematic representation of hydrolyzed polyacrylonitrile) determines the level of crosslinking of CH-COO and the viscosity of the resulting polymer. Exceeding this value in a ratio of 10: 1 leads to the transformation of the polymer into a solid (rubber-like) mass[7,10].

CONCLUSION

Thus, organosilicon compounds based on industrial secondary raw materials and tetraethoxysilane have been synthesized. Compositions of hydrophobic compositions based on synthesized polymer the measures are designed and tested in concrete mixes.

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THE OCCUPATION OF EXPERIENCES AND PLEASANTRY NETWORKS IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF RECORDS IN ADVENTURES

Prof. S.V.M. Sharma

Indian Management School And Research Center In Mumbai/India

ABSTRACT: This article hopes to know the occupation of experiences and associations of affability in the country's accounts among a social affair of monetary trained professionals and heads having a spot with various business relationship in Lima. These bits of knowledge, depictions and experiences were made inside the construction of the proposition "Assessment of the discussion on Peruvian culture in the principal business relationship of Lima". Appropriately, research starts from the need to consider the most extraordinary spaces of Peruvian culture from human sciences since it helps with perceiving how power is drilled in Latin America.

KEYWORDS: Congeniality associations, improvement of records, attempts.

INTRODUCTION

The data was got later a movement of conversations with cash administrators and bosses auxiliary with different business relationship in Lima, Peru. In them, the interviewees were drawn nearer to draw an equivalent between their master lives close by the political setting they expected to live and develop a record. Thus, it was possible to know how the tops of the rule financial affiliations crosscountry at the beginning of this century think about the Peruvian country. The goal was to know how the tops of the essential monetary affiliations crosscountry around the beginning of this century envision the Peruvian country. This under the going with requests: what is the socio-political setting that begins these experiences and depictions of Peruvian business pioneers around the beginning of the 21st century? What depictions do these people have about Peruvian culture and the performers that structure it? How do your own experiences relate to the age of these bits of knowledge and depictions? This grants us to

perceive how the vision of the country in Peruvian culture has changed, from a transcendent class (Cotler, 1978) to a trend-setter in the different field to unravel a country vision, making it definitive.

For this article, we talked with various people from the Lima business region to look into their master callings inside the group environment of the country. Some can be depicted as accounts and others as through and through gatherings. In that sense, we share the most expansive features to help the peruser contextualize. Twenty interviews were driven with finance administrators and heads. The range of each one depended upon the components and a couple of focuses created. All respondents live in Lima, with by far most of the conversations in the Lima areas of San Isidro, Miraflores and Surco. Of the 20 respondents, 6 have a spot with industry, 4 to exchange, 4 to mining and the rest are in fishing, cultivation and advancing. Because of industrialists, branches, for instance, materials, pieces of clothing, metalworking, beverages and food were covered. By then, on the business side, most of the people having a spot with this space held regulatory positions. Taking as reference the property, there are two get-togethers: the people who are associated with the obligation regarding associations and the managers responsible for corporate organization. The past are seen as those people who make an authority decisions since they or their family finally keep up ownership and control. Dependent upon the case, the control is selected to an untouchable for the association of your business, there being a comfortable association between the two. Executives are any individual expertly used to include the most imperative circumstances in powerful inside corporate organization. They have no liability regarding, they are utilized by the owners, yet they are expertly ready to make due. This is reflected in, for example, that all heads met have supervisors and graduates in Senior Management.

All through Republican history, the coordinated effort among monetary subject matter experts and public performers has been steady and fluid (Durand, 2018). Of these, the social orders can be considered to be the substance of a particular get-together inverse the rest of society. Consequently, understanding its arrangement of encounters helps with understanding which cycles are the most huge in the advancement of a country vision. The history of business affiliations concerning establishments is reasonably later: between 1884-1895. In that period, the

Lima Chamber of Commerce was imagined as recipient of the past Colonial Consulate Court, a component that mediated trade disputes. During the twentieth century, the association among owners and public specialists was close considering the way that the Lima Chamber of Commerce was the singular affiliation and functioned as an association between the political world and the business world. A brief time frame later, the past Agriculture and Mining Society is detached into three free affiliations: the National Agrarian Society, the National Society of Industries and the National Mining Society because the state progression work environments required independent affiliations that could be at their own speed.

RESULTS

On the other hand, the course of their relatives around their advantages, by and large academic or their business capacities, is routinely included. In that sense, one ought to get his put because following what one has would mean being mediocre and living off past achievements. The primary explanation is: "children ought to beat watchmen in regards to accomplishment." If people don't work in business, it should be in another field because the critical thing is to make merits. In association with business, many were ready in exclusive organizations yet referred to that there should be no benefits and should start from underneath. For example, paying little mind to being her father one of the setting up accessories, an industrialist says that she started from the base as a programmer and her German adolescence offers a movement of characteristics, for instance, dependability and troublesome work, there is a persevering demeanor to regard The name of the grandparents.

CONCLUSION

We can reason that, first, experiences arise in the going with spaces: families, informative centers, and master affiliations. Inside these spots, the get-together is solid because to the extent that business visionaries associate with finance managers, they structure a "ordinary soul" and proposition specific characteristics. The imagined by these spaces serves to arrange into Peruvian culture yet isolating itself with the ultimate objective of leading. On the other hand, casual associations are worked all through the starting periods of master getting ready.

These are reinforced as each individual changes them as shown by the objectives set. The individual can therefore "exploit" the use of these associations to further develop their contacts both inside the business world and in various circles of public action.

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PRINCIPLES OF TAX LEGISLATION

Kozimbek Goziev

Lecturer Department of Administrative And Financial Law, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: This article describes the tax principles existing in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In it, the principles of taxation are explained. Examples from the practice are also given during the interpretation.

KEYWORDS: Tax, tax principles, taxation, peculiarities of the tax system, Normative legal acts.

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, we can see the peculiarities of the tax system in its principles. Like any state activity, taxation is carried out based on certain principles. Principles of the tax system is one of the forms of determining the legitimacy and using it with common sense. If the principles of the tax system are violated, it directly hinders the solution of practical tasks. The principles of the tax system are diverse and closely related to each other. Tax legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the following principles:

Obligation to pay taxes

Taxpayer-legal entities and individuals are obliged to pay taxes and other mandatory payments established by the tax code (this situation arises from the requirement of the constitutional norm);

The accuracy of taxation, that is, every taxpayer should know exactly which taxes and other mandatory payments the taxpayer must pay, when, how much and in what order, the elements of taxes and mandatory payments must be identified. (For example, according to the tax code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the amount of tax on the property of individuals is calculated based on the value of inventory and at a fixed rate according to the state of the property in 1 January. The tax on the property of individuals for buildings, buildings and structures, which is the total share property of several owners, is paid by each of the owners in proportion to their

share in these buildings, buildings and structures. The tax rate is determined by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the appropriate order. Payment of the tax on the property of individuals for the tax period is carried out until 15 October of the reporting year).

Fairness of tax evasion

Taxation in general, the definition of privileges on taxes and other mandatory payments must comply with the principles of social justice. It is not allowed to grant individual property benefits on taxes and other mandatory payments. Taxes and other mandatory payments may not be of a discriminatory nature and may not be applied on the basis of social, racial, national, religious and other similar criteria. For example, the sole entrepreneur A. It is not possible to give preference to Akhmedov or the production enterprise "EAST" on exemption from property taxes or other taxes and mandatory payments. The privilege is defined as the exemption from the land tax of a certain category, for example, persons with disabilities and participants in the war, as well as persons equated to them whose scope is determined by the legislation, or the exemption from the profit tax of certain manufacturers, for example, treatment under treatment institutions, production workshops;

The uniqueness of the tax system

The tax system is unique to all taxpayers throughout the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Within the customs territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taxes and other mandatory payments that directly or indirectly restrict the free circulation of goods (works, services) or financial funds are not allowed to be established;

Transparency of legislation on Taxation

Normative legal acts regulating taxation issues must be published in official publications. For all, not officially declared normative legal acts as a document that does not enter into force do not bring legal consequences and can serve as a basis for the regulation of relations in the tax sphere, the application of any sanctions for non-compliance with the instructions in them;

Presumption of the right of the taxpayer – all inconsistencies and inaccuracies that can not be eliminated in the documents of the tax law-be interpreted in favor of the taxpayer.

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PERSISTING NAIVENESS AS A DESPONDENCY OF GROAN CARRIAGE

Dr. Muhammad Basheer

Partner Professor, Dept. Of Fashion Management Studies, National Institute Of Fashion Technology, Mangattuparamba, Kannur, Kerala

ABSTRACT: Honesty as portrayed in the Merriam-Webster word reference is „the planning to acknowledge the instances of others without satisfactory evidence“. As patients will generally acknowledge their prosperity expert community too speedily, chances of are by and large successfully dumbfounded. From now on, it was proper to separate the force of patient naïveté in this assessment. Understanding straightforwardness, through phenomenological research, was described in regards to trust, conviction, quiet submission and indeed approach towards the subject matter expert. Data assessment uncovered that out of the total respondents who checked out the examination, for all intents and purposes half of them would in general conveniently acknowledge and consent to their clinical expert association. An enormous differentiation existed between respondents having various levels of clinical care similarly as those yielded in facilities having a spot with north, central and south Kerala in respect of their straightforwardness, from the eventual outcomes of single heading ANOVA.

KEYWORDS: Non-complainers, trust, passive consent, clinical care.

INTRODUCTION

Honesty as a variable to explain the traits of a „inexperienced consumer“ have been referred to in the composing identifying with client protection of western purchaser promotes (The Consumer Protection Handbook, USA 2004). The Canadian Supreme Court (2012) described the unsophisticated client as "a customary, hurried purchaser, who isn't particularly skillful at distinguishing deceptions or subtleties found in business depictions". A typical level of carefulness, interest and knowledge portrays the reasonable client. Accepting these characteristics to a conviction organization like clinical benefits, it was suitable to see whether

any enormous association existed between open minded artlessness and protesting conduct. As patients will more often than not acknowledge their prosperity expert association too immediately, chances of are by and large viably duped. Hence, it was proper to look at the power of patient artlessness in this assessment. A 5-thing scale was made to evaluate the patient honesty.

Grumbling customers and non-whimpering customers were isolated by Heung and Lam (2003) in light of a couple of reasons. They tracked down that the perspectives in grumbling consolidate searching for survey, articulation of disappointment or compensation referencing medicinal movement and conveying energetic dismay. Voorhees et al (2006) analyzed the non-fussing behavior and observed that customers may not whimper because of reasons like late affirmation of the mistake, purchaser reliability, firm"s reputation for quality, inside attributions, social components like too involved to even think about evening consider protest and presence of buddies, elective movement of brand trading, etc Some frustrated customers may not fuss clearly to the expert association. Their reasons were found as whimpering was not worth the time and effort, or they didn't have even the remotest clue where or how to fuss or they acknowledged that nothing would be done whether or not they protested in any way shape or form.

Objections

- I. To inspect the association of ongoing sincerity with their monetary and section factors
- II. ii. To consider the association that understanding guilelessness has with open minded movement post frustration
- III. iii. To find whether there is any relationship among naïveté and zone to which the center where they were surrendered has a spot, say North, Central and South Kerala
- IV. iv. To find whether there is any relationship among naïveté and patient"s clinical care

- V. v. To take a gander at the association between long term straightforwardness and nature of clinical facility in which they are surrendered, state, private and accommodating

METHODS

This examination is exploratory in nature and targets finding the honesty of inaptients which discourage them from fussing post dissatisfaction. The quantity of occupants in the examination was the patients or their onlookers who had benefitted changed organizations of any private or pleasant crisis facility in Kerala during their visit and baffled with any of these organizations. This is a post purchase study and data was assembled during the 0-6 months of their delivery from the facility. The testing methodology followed was probability reviewing. The data variety instrument was coordinated and self-coordinated survey gathered from the analyzed nine districts of Kerala.

Inquiries as for space of the center, nature of the crisis facility (whether or not private or supportive), number of extended lengths of stay as long term, regardless of whether the patient had gone through any operation during the stay and their selfassessment of clinical care were asked. Moreover, data identifying with eight monetary and fragment factors were also accumulated. The private and accommodating crisis centers with at any rate 100 beds were considered in the last model. For this assessment, the entire region of Kerala was separated into three zones viz. North, Central and South Kerala. Out of the 14 districts in Kerala, nine locales were considered, three each from three zones.

RESULTS

Various connections using Tukey HSD tests uncovered that the respondents who were surrendered in facilities having a spot with south Kerala had a mean artlessness level that was in a general sense higher than that for the other two social events and were not exactly equivalent to those yielded in centers having a spot with north and central Kerala. Accordingly, these two social affairs didn't shift from each other when pondered pair canny.

A quantifiably gigantic differentiation was seen between respondents having a spot with various age get-togethers, enlightening and word related levels, intimate status and with changing levels of clinical care and those yielded in different kinds of clinical centers having a spot with different districts of Kerala in respect of patient sincerity. In any case, there was no clear difference between respondents subject to sex, money related status, religion and nature of spot of stay in respect of patient guilelessness.

A basic differentiation in the artlessness levels of respondents having medium-care and obliviousness shows that the pleasant nature increases when they see themselves to have little data about the scientific and accommodating strategy. In addition, respondents surrendered in crisis facilities having a spot with south Kerala were found to have a substitute level of guilelessness when stood out from their northern and central accomplices. Subsequently, these centers might devise measures to engage plain protesting conduct with the objective that they comprehend the reasons of frustration of their inpatients and accordingly devise measures to reduce the same.

CONCLUSION

The patient honesty was assessed using a 5-point Likert scale. In the wake of calculating a summated score of the scale, to some degree short of what one-piece of the respondents (43.9 percent) were significantly artless while fairly more than one-fourth of the respondents had a spot with the honorably unsophisticated (29.2 percent) and especially careful classes (26.9 percent). Along these lines, we can assume that out of the outright respondents who participated in the examination, essentially half of them would in general successfully acknowledge and consent to their clinical expert association.

Subsequent to playing out an association test to find the association among straightforwardness and complaining behavior, a gigantic positive relationship was found between the two variables. There was verification to communicate that an enormous difference existed between respondents having various levels of clinical care in respect of their naïveté, from the outcomes of single bearing ANOVA. In addition, an enormous qualification was found

among respondents surrendered in clinical facilities having a spot with north, central and south Kerala in respect of patient honesty. Different relationships using Tukey HSD tests revealed that the authentic differentiations won between respondents having medium care and high obliviousness about the characteristic and helpful technique similarly as between the people who were yielded in crisis facilities having a spot with south Kerala from those in north and central Kerala.

CONCLUSION

Clinical benefits region with everything taken into account and centers explicitly should endeavor to fathom the level of honesty of the patients. Customer course of action may be done by itemizing some instrument and customer association strategies should be created to serve each class better. Measures may moreover be taken in showing the customers, especially patients or their spectators with the objective that they don't get easily flabbergasted by restricted time offers of various brands.

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UZBEK LANGUAGE FOR CENTURIES

Odina Sanakulova

Uzbekistan Journalism And Mass Communications University, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: This article covers the stages of development of the Uzbek language. From its initial development, the traversal paths are explained by changes. During the reading of the article you will learn interesting and important information about the Uzbek language.

KEYWORDS: Literary language, state language, rules of literary language, old Uzbek, current literary language, old Turkish language.

*Insonni soʻz ayladi judo hayvondin,
Bilim, guhari sharifroq yoʻq andin
(A.Navoiy).*

INTRODUCTION

Language is the pride of a nation, a nation without a language, too, society is morally degraded. What ended the fate of the peoples who lost their language is known to us from history: those who were forced to accept the language of the nation that lay down for themselves, and at the same time to accept its customs. In order not to fall into a similar negative situation, the heads of State carried out actions aimed at keeping the language of the people, the language of the nation pure, its place and importance even higher.

What periods and processes have passed before the present Uzbek literary language appeared today, how the attitude towards the Uzbek language has developed, we found it appropriate to speak briefly about it.

As studied by linguists, the Uzbek language belongs to the Turkish family of languages, which initially began to be used as a Turkish language. The first written sources written in this language have been preserved to this day. These are the following: “Kultegin”, “Bilga Khakon”. The

history of writing these inscriptions dates back to the VI-VII centuries BC (the countries of East and West Turkestan). So the roots of the development of our current Uzbek language date back to the Middle Ages.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The role of rare masterpieces such as “Devonu ligotit turk”, “Kutadgu bilig”, “Hibatul Hakoyik”, which were written in the X—XI centuries, in the further development of the Uzbek language, which began to form as a separate language, is incomparable in its deep integration into the living language of the people. In particular, Mahmud Koshgari used the proverb “language of the beginning of morality” (language of the head of decency) in his work “Devani lugotit turk” and showed how the role of language in the life of the people is incomparable. In addition, Mahmud Koshgari analyzed the dictionary of Turkic languages in his work, in which 7500 word comments took place. It is from this period that we can say that the history of Turkic language learning has also begun.

At a later stage of development, a number of scientific and artistic-scientific works were created, which also made a significant contribution to the development of the Turkic language. In particular, a number of creative products created in the XII— XIII centuries, such as “Devoni Hikmat”, “Qissai Rabguziy”, “Muhabbatnama”, “Mehrojnama”, “Muqaddimat-ul adab”, “Yusuf va Zulayho”, “Oguznama” were enriched with the Uzbek language and its so-called local dialects.

The Turkic language, more precisely, is associated with the radical turn in the development of the Uzbek language, the great success of the “Sultan of the word estate” – the name and efforts of Mir Alisher Navoi. Not only Alisher Navoi, but also Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Turdi Faragiy, Baburahim Mashrab, Zokirjon Kholmuhammad Oglu Furqat, Muhammad Aminkhuja Muqimiy also have great services in bringing the old Uzbek language to a new stage of development. In particular, the work carried out by Alisher Navoi in this regard and the attitude towards it are incomparable. The fact that “Sultan of the word property “speaks Uzbek as a treasure” is proof of the great respect he has for him. It is worth noting that at the time of

Alisher Navoi's life, there were various threats to the Uzbek language, and in this situation he cleaned the nation's "treasure" from "snakes" and "thorns" and showed great courage both for the Turkic peoples and for the Uzbek people. Alisher Navoi in his work "Muhokamat ul-kugotayn" compared the possibilities of the Uzbek language, its special features and other languages.

The development of the Uzbek language took place in the 20th century in Aloh at the later stage. The fact that the Uzbek language was directly influenced by the colonial system during this period indicates that the situation was much more complicated. Abdurauf Fitrat, Gazi Alim Yunusov, Uygun Tursunov, E. in formation and development of Uzbek linguistics in the 20th century. The services of Polivanov, Qayum Ramazon, Fahri Kamolov and Ayub Gulumov are great. During this period, such unique and rare works as Abdurauf Fitrat's socio-publicist works, which were considered rare works of the Uzbek people, Abdulla Qadiri's "O'tkan kunlar", Chulpan's "Kecha va kunduz", Said Ahmad's "Jimjitlik", Gafur Ghulom's "Shum bola" Khudayberdi Tukhtaboyev's "Sariq devni minib" were created.

The importance of the Uzbek language, which has lost a certain role, as well as attempts to restore and strengthen its position, ended in the 80-ies of the last century with the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language. It is from this historical event that the people's language has passed different stages of historical development, sometimes it was insulted, sometimes it was forgotten and the Uzbek language was given life again.

Today it has been almost 32 years since the Uzbek language was granted the status of the state language. In this past period, a number of reforms have been carried out and are being implemented aimed at studying the history of our language, reconsidering its dictionary richness, grammatical, morphological, methodological aspects, shaping it as an understandable and nationalistic language for each of its citizens. In particular, the adoption of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the state language". By law, the right of citizens to freely choose the language of treatment, the language of education, the language of activity were guaranteed, the status of the Uzbek language as the state language was strengthened once

again. Friendly norms, such as respect for the languages of other nations and peoples in our country, along with the Uzbek language, were also reflected in the law.

CONCLUSION

The systematic implementation of measures by the heads of state aimed at increasing the role and importance of the Uzbek language and ensuring its destruction is evidenced by the fact that attention is paid to the Uzbek language at the state level. By the first president Islam Karimov: "... self-awareness, expression of national consciousness and thinking, spiritual and spiritual connection between generations is manifested through language. In total, noble qualities are absorbed into the human soul by the language, by the mother-in-law, by the unique charm of the native language. The fact that his mother tongue is the spirit of this nation," said President SHavkat Mirziyoyev: "how many centuries have passed since our ancestors cares about the prosperity and prospects of our native language — this means that the nation understands itself, struggles to raise its spiritual perfection. The reputation of the state language is the reputation of the whole people and society as a whole," he said, adding that this is a practical proof of our speech.

P.Q: but how do we react to our Uzbek literary language, which has passed through the pass of centuries? Mixed support of words belonging to different languages in our speech (without understanding the meaning), do not we disrespect our native language?

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INVESTIGATION OF MISSHAPEN UNSYMMETRICAL AND PRESERVATION LABORER

Sahil Kumar Gola

Aide Professor, Deptt.Of E&C Engg. , MIT Moradabad, Ram Ganga Vihar, Phase-II,
Moradabad (244001), India

ABSTRACT: Ordinarily a part of the perilous and various tasks is unimaginable by human. As such there is need for change in present time. In this manner, robot can be a respectable and feasible decision for hazardous purposes. Robot accepts various positions in different fields of undertakings, clinical, colleges, home machines and military and defend. The proposed work is to plan and develop an undesirable scene dreadful little animal robot. As of now daily's robot's comes in the market works on an essential domain while we are on an endeavor which manages plain surface comparably horrendous surface, for instance, forest area, slanting and unpredictable zones. In this paper we are focusing in on the use of upsetting scene machines instead of using other clear robots. This paper in like manner presents a Preservation robot which uses different headways like Infrared sensor, PIR sensor Ultrasonic sensor, Bluetooth module and Wifi Technology, etc and this paper proposed a low voltage power supply, straightforwardness and distant machine which is controlled using microcontroller and Android Application.

KEYWORDS: Microcontroller, IR Sensor, PIR Sensor, Bluetooth Technology, Wi-Fi Technology.

INTRODUCTION

With the improvement of world the development is redesigned bit by bit with the sensible endeavors and capable work towards by making of machines. This paper presents multipurpose functionalities of distant machines. These days for controlling and progression of machines various developments are used, for instance, Zigbee shows, RF modules, Touch screen, WiFi modules and various advances. In this paper we inspected thmisshapen distinctive investigates

what improvement has been done in cutting edge mechanics in field of Misshapen region and Preservation Laborers and our proposed work as for the going with paper.

The entire control is abided with the microcontroller. Moreover, bomb area, bomb scattering, gas spillage acknowledgment, live human body ID and squeezing factor weapon are consolidated. In this, the machine can travel thmisshapen the unpredictable surfaces as well. The control of the machine from far off region is done with a PC. The information to the PC is finished by the state of the art development named Zigbee Technology.

An electronic shield machine building is organized, that has a laser weapon joined, which is utilized for pointing laser bars to destroy the goal article. Maybe the most compelling things about these robots is that they have the ability to perform missions indirectly in the field, with no certified danger to living spirits. In the proposed structure, a robot is developed that is controlled thmisshapen Microcontroller. For the pointing reason and to see the road and the ecological elements where the robot is journeying, distant cameras are presented. Radio repeat can be used to control the machine. These insurance robots used in military are normally used with the fused system including gripper, cameras and sensors. This is particularly planned for watch mechanized system to save human life and safeguard the country from adversaries. In the current structures, PC using ZigBee show is used to screen the robot.

METHODS

A large number individuals nowadays approach phones and thus the world for sure has turned into an overall town. Out of nowhere, a particular individual can be reached with the mobile phone. New turns of events and contemplations can be created from it that can moreover further develop its capacities. Progressions, for instance, Infra-red, Bluetooth, WiFi which has made actually goes to show the very reality that improvements are in all honesty possible and these updates have worked with our day by day everyday practice and the way where we experience. Distant organization of a couple of home and office machines is a subject of creating interest and actually we have seen various systems giving such controls. Compact machines will be robots which can move around and speak with their present situation and not

just turned to a particular spot. There are various labs and assessment packs from various universities and adventures which are completely dedicated on investigating versatile robots, because of their monstrous potential and moved application in industry, military, security, and entertainment.

The machine is uncommonly expected for observation reason. The control instrument is outfitted close by video transmission office. The video transmission is all things considered, achieved thmissshapen quick picture transmission. From the get go, the robot will be furnished with an Android progressed cell which will get the circumstance before it and will move the photos to the laborer on which the customer will be controlling and watching the live feed.

In this endeavor, they focused in on the limit of the sensors to recognize the extent of objects of level surfaces and of different materials. The assessments show that the straightforwardness US and IR sensors can give strong distance assessment. The results got show OK course of action between the Phong Illumination model and the veritable data got in the endorsement tests. It has been demonstrated that US sensor has to some degree more significant standard than that of the IR sensor, especially for little distance assessment inside their usable ranges. Contrasts between the conscious distances and real distances show fundamental re-change. More thought should be taken while setting the things from the sensors during getting data since the little change in point could show entirely unexpected distance than the genuine one. The abundancy from the US sensor is dependent on the distance and course of the obstacle relative with the sensor, where little heading of the reflecting surface has relatively little effect on the IR sensor plentifulness. In any case, the ampleness from the IR sensor is dependent upon the reflectivity of the impediment, where surface tone and flawlessness has relatively little effect on the yield signal from the US sensor.

CONCLUSION

The proposed robot has degree of inevitable current, gatekeeper and home applications. It will in general be used to separate the environment of a coal mine with no human intervention. It can in like manner be used in a detainee situation to leave point the particular space of

manipulators with the help of ultrasonic and PIR sensor, saving various lives during rescue mission. Another application is home security structure to recognize improvement of intruder thmissshapen PIR sensor. Various focal points of this structure are its extent of action up to 100m, secure data move ought to be conceivable with the help of Bluetooth Module and Android Application. Entire endeavor will help in Military and Preservation assignments, for instance, human distinguishing proof, distance assessment, impediment area and besides due to their bug like wheels it can go in all scenes.

Assertion

The maker offers his sincere gratitude to Professor Pragati Gupta of the division of Electronic and Communication Engineering at Moradabad establishment of Technology for his significant admonishment and bearing all thmissshapen the endeavor. Thankful are a result of Professor Amit Saxena for his accommodating recommendations for his steady assistance to complete the endeavor adequately. At long last maker should thanks their people for their coordinated effort.

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ELECTRONIC EDUCATION IN SPORTS

Abbosjon I. Soyibnazarov

Head Of The Center For Digital Educational Technologies, Fergana Branch Of The Uzbek State University Of Physical Culture And Sports, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: Currently, the process of forming an information society, which aims to informatize the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is underway. For free navigation in information flows, a modern specialist of any profile must be able to receive, process and use data using computers, telecommunications and other information technologies. This is especially true for physical education and sports professionals.

KEYWORDS: Information, communication, technology, scientific-technical, potential, object, normative-technical.

INTRODUCTION

Despite certain difficulties in the organizational, logistical, scientific and methodological aspects of the development and introduction of modern technologies in the field of physical culture and sports, they are of particular interest to a number of specialists, as well as in other fields. It is necessary to move from traditional means to the use of modern information and communication technologies that allow more efficient collection, processing and transmission of information, independent work and self-education, qualitative change of content. Methods and organizational forms of training, training of highly qualified athletes and referees, physical education and health work with the population.

The main purpose of informatization is to qualitatively change the education system in order to prepare citizens for life in the information society. This is achieved through the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities that enable each member of society to have the potential to freely access and interact with legitimate open information using information technology appropriate

to the current level of scientific, technological and economic development of a particular individual. State

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In this regard, there are certain requirements to the education system, the educational process, the general communicative and information culture of teachers and educators, as well as information technologies of education and upbringing, forms and methods of their application in the educational process. warms up.

Meeting these requirements should lead to the creation of a fundamentally new information culture, which implies the ability to properly use the whole set of information technologies in their professional activities.

This includes the development and implementation of professionally oriented software and software-pedagogical tools and courses aimed at acquiring the necessary knowledge for the educational process of physical education faculties and institutes, as well as personal experience in their use in professional activities. requires a cloak. pedagogical and sports activities.

In solving the problem of informatization of education and the educational process, the following should be clearly defined:

- Where and for what purpose to use the capabilities of personal computers, information and communication technologies;
- what software products should provide solutions to the problems of informatization of teaching and learning process;
- Development and use of software and pedagogical tools in the professional and pedagogical activities of physical education and sports specialists;
- Search, processing, storage, transmission and presentation of educational and scientific-methodological information in the field of physical culture and sports with the help of modern information and communication technologies.

Means of information and communication technologies in the field of physical culture and sports - software based on microprocessors, computer technology, modern means and systems of information and information exchange, software and hardware, as well as activities in the field of physical culture and sports. 'minlash; collection, collection, storage, processing, transmission and production of information and access to information resources of computer networks.

Informatization and communication tools for the purposes of physical education and training - means of information and communication technologies, used in conjunction with educational-methodical, normative-technical and organizational-instructional materials, ensuring the implementation of optimal technology of their pedagogical use.

Computer visualization of educational information on physical culture is a visual representation of an object, its main parts or models on the screen and, if necessary, a graphical interpretation of the studied laws of the object or process being studied (all type). angles, details, by demonstrating the internal interdependence of components) in development, in time and space motion.

The main directions of the use of information technology in physical culture and sports are primarily related to:

- with the development of the individual and the training of future professionals for a prosperous life in the information society;
- Implementation of the social order for specialists in the field of physical culture and sports through the informatization of physical culture and sports;
- by activating all levels of education and upbringing

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as in all areas, the role of computers and information technology in sports is very important. In the effective conduct of training and preparation for competitions.

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DISSEMINATION ONCOLOGY TUTORING AND CONTRIBUTION WITH THE FRESHMAN OBJECTIVE SITUATION

Sama Essa

English Department, College Of Arts And Social Sciences, Sultan Qaboos University,
Oman

ABSTRACT: The target of this examination was to choose the impact and experience of dissemination oncology guidance in the freshman objective inclusion with the USA. A once-over of American objective schools was agreed from various sources including the Association of American Medical Colleges and American Association of Colleges of Osteopathic Medicine in the mid year of 2009. Data was taken out through foundation site overview, solitary calls and email dissemination. A total of 198 undertakings were consolidated. Each objective school instructive arrangement had oncology address during MS year 1 and 2, yet an irrelevant aggregate had a RO-express talk during MS year 1 and 2. There were gigantic differences in the RO preparing and association with allopathic versus osteopathic programs. Home flow oncology ventures and calling urging were connected with a dissemination oncology elective during year 3 and 4.

KEYWORDS: Circulation oncology; guidance; freshman objective tutoring.

INTRODUCTION

Threat is the resulting driving justification behind death all over the planet, and influences essentially every field of medicine. While a couple of objective strong points may be locked in with the thought of threatening development patients, oncologists, dissemination oncologists, and experts stay the three standard backbones of infection treatment in prescription. Course treatment is used for the treatment of generally 50% of all patients with infection and records for over 40% of the fix rates. Past assessments have shown a shortfall of oncology guidance in the freshman objective situation. Plus, course oncology remains a little degree of the oncology informational experience for objective understudies. Various activities have attempted to

extend presentation sure to RO are in periods of progress or possibly execution, yet it is dark how strong these have been. The target of this examination was to conclude the effect on RO preparing and association with the freshman objective contribution with the USA.

Strategy An overview of American objective schools was concurred from various sources including the Association of American Medical Colleges and American Association of Colleges of Osteopathic Medicine in the mid year of 2019. Later the basic summary was made, schools with different grounds were converged into one region. Objective schools that were actually settled and had no graduating class were banished from the assessment. A total of 198 activities were associated with this examination. Data was removed from various sources including the school's site, calls, and messages. Key ascribes were accumulated including MD or DO program, RO program with or without occupants, RO unequivocal vested party, oncology addresses including RO-express talk during MS1-2, RO rotations electives during MS3-4, livelihood consultants for RO, and match into a RO residency program.

DISCUSSION

Our assessment shows the change of RO education and inclusion with freshman objective preparing. Though all objective school instructive plans have oncology-based discussions, very few schools have a RO express talk. Past examinations have shown for all intents and purposes no relationship of flow oncologists in the educational piece of the freshman objective experience. Another review shows 60.8% of objective understudies had no receptiveness to RO. This presents brief zone of progress for our field. There was a frail connection between pre objective RO preparing with home RO divisions' occupants, which might show an uncommon interest in guidance in these workplaces. More assessments are critical to understand the effect of home RO programs on instructive arrangement improvement during the underlying two years of objective school. Moreover, disclosures suggest tremendous fluctuateneces between the allopathic and osteopathic objective schools were found. Understudies at osteopathic objective schools have less receptiveness to RO both in their pre objective and objective years. Confined RO transparency and the extended competitiveness of RO might explain this basic qualification.

To further develop RO informative preparing, oncology schooling with everything taken into account should be improved. Review have set up that oncology-related tutoring stays under-underlined stood out from various subjects, and objective understudies are not as okay with oncology when appeared differently in relation to various orders. Objective schools might need to retool oncology instruction for the state of the art objective understudies in light of the association of dangerous development with various fields. Also, RO workplaces with both insightful and private practice providers should contact their objective schools to assist with making instructive arrangement suitable for each and every objective understudy. Past assessments have displayed incredible outcomes with this option. On account of the augmentation of new objective schools, public RO associations, for instance, ASTRO and ACRO can make widespread addresses that can be used by objective schools to work on instructive program, especially if they don't have a set up home RO office. Considering everything, RO tutoring during the educational portion of the freshman objective experience stays extremely limited. This obstacle is substantially more expressed in objective schools without RO mentorship and in osteopathic objective schools. This shortfall of RO receptiveness supports itself via conveying less understudies into the field. These issues require thought both on a public and objective school-express level.

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FORMATION OF GEOGRAPHICAL KNOWLEDGE IN VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS

Dilshod A. Musaev

Independent researcher Tashkent state pedagogical university named after Nizami. Teacher of the boarding school no 77 specialized for the visually impaired people, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: The article reviews the processes, features, stages, problems and solution of knowledge development on geography among students with visual disability.

Visually impaired students' knowledge, skills, qualifications, competence, perception are analyzed.

The pedagogical process is abstract and theoretical; for its implementation it is necessary to create a specific model, and on its basis it is possible to create a specific pedagogical technology [1; 382-b].

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, skills, qualifications, see, listen, feel, distraction.

INTRODUCTION

To our view, the process of forming geographical knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies of blind and visually impaired students takes place in 4 stages.

The process of formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies of a students with visual defects.

Stages	Processes
1-	students receive information they see, listen, feel and etc
2-	information in the minds of students is processed through the analysis-synthesis (imagination and understanding are developed)
3-	received knowledge is transferred to others (it will be explained)

4-	possessed knowledge is converted to qualifications, skills and competencies through application in everyday life
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The organization of successful educational activities at all stages of the process of knowledge formation allows the student to acquire quality knowledge and be able to use it in everyday life. However, inappropriate activities of educators and students at different stages of the educational process lead to insufficient formation of knowledge. For example, knowledge may not be accepted by students in the first stage due to the fact that in the first stage the student does not fully master the information (material) given by the teacher (distraction, etc.). Our experiments with visually impaired schoolchildren show that 50% of students complete the acquisition of knowledge in the first stage.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The solution to this problem can be found by the teacher using correction-oriented methods. For example, the teacher can focus the student's attention on the material using practical methods and tools (working with a customized map and ICT, working individually, collaboratively, and in small groups). The given materials should be carefully organized. To do this, teacher asks students specific questions during and at the end of the information study.

In the second stage, there might be cases when a learner is unable to analyze and synthesize information due to a complete lack of understanding of the material received (lack of concepts and ideas to prove in his mind, life experience (pre-existing knowledge), etc.), resulting in information not being assimilated and knowledge formation interrupted.

In visually impaired students, it is necessary to develop a qualitative content of theoretical knowledge and knowledge of key words (terms), which allows students to quickly and accurately understand the given material and think consciously.

In the third stage, the student may not be able to communicate what he or she knows to the teacher and others because of his or her emotional state and so on. These shortcomings are overcome by developing the student's self-confidence, presentation skills, artistry, speech skills.

In the fourth stage, visually impaired students are unable to apply their knowledge in familiar and unfamiliar situations in their daily lives due to lack or incomplete adaptation of the necessary tools (specially adapted geographical maps, ICT tools, etc.). It is necessary to provide students with specially adapted maps and ICT tools and to develop the skills and abilities to use

them in the performance of life tasks, so that the students of the studied category can apply geographical knowledge in their lives.

CONCLUSION

In short, the process of acquiring geographical knowledge content in students with severe visual impairment is complicated when the information obtained at the above stages is not related to the concepts and ideas in the mind, the concepts are abstract and fragmentary, and secondary defects exist. The teacher must fully control the process at all stages of knowledge formation in students, take into account the individual and differential characteristics of students, cognitive abilities and, if necessary, achieve corrective orientation of students' knowledge of teaching technologies and methods. We have relied on the compensatory activities of sensory analyzers, the development and introduction of correction-oriented methods and tools in the formation of students' knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of introducing new technologies of teaching geography.

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ENLIGHTENING EVALUATION IN THE PULSE OF COMPUTE

Tayeb Salih

Education Department, Faculty Of Social Science, The National Ribat University Khartoum,
Sudan

ABSTRACT: Generally informative speculation and execution are depicted by wild awkwardness. This not simply reflects conflicting incorporation in and benefits by development (in the past implied as the "progressed hole") yet likewise embodies age-old unbalanced attributes between and inside nations, spread by inappropriate structures and one-sided rehearses. Fittingly, the good mark of 'cutting edge esteem' can't be cultivated in separation: the major injustices (noticeably informational unbalanced qualities) ought to at first be restored, thusly giving an obvious goal to automated thought.

KEYWORDS: Digitization, Educational venture, Educational Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Significant DISPARITIES IN THE DIGITAL AGE

The world, countries inside it, associations inside and across those countries, and thusly people's lives, are being – and will, significantly and generally erratically, continue to be – radically changed by unendingly rapidly propelling development, therefore by Compute. The World Economic Forum's originator uncovers to us that "... we stay close to the actual edge of an inventive insurrection that will from an overall perspective change the manner in which we live, work, and relate to one another... in its scale, degree, and complexity, the change will be not typical for anything humanity has experienced already".

It would be guileless not to see that earlier presumptions that electronic media would engage the billions to become overall town occupants have lamentably shown unusual. Tricky, ruffian

and savage direct are expanded by the web and intensified through the counter well disposed interferences of electronic media. Possibly, we are at the constraint of a period of generally prominence based associations – but entering and liking that emerging age ought to be joined by insightful careful steps and a fitting overall framework to direct the assorted social and information networks is easier said than initiated. As such Zuboff alerts against the "more significant, ruinous predations of observation private venture" and Brindle talks about "our broke viewpoints, fighting fundamentalisms, crippling of federal retirement aide's, and uncertainty of one another".

We are as of now no ifs, ands or buts in VUCA conditions, depicted by capriciousness, weakness, unpredictability and vulnerability, exemplified by broad digitization. Various enthusiastic portrayals have been drawn and different wonderful assessments shaped. Regardless, shortfall of accessibility makes progressed advancements hard for the vast majority of various peoples, while the huge costs of data and voice bunches make them over the top. There similarly are constant progressed parcels across sexual direction, geology, age, and pay estimations inside every country.

Hypothetical free venture, Uberised and Amazonified working conditions, and the looming post human economy might perhaps get comfortable and demolish unevenness – both inside and between nations, particularly between the industrialized and making world. There are hopeful theories about headway – about an uncommon mechanical bound forward or about protesters' ability to bounce ages held somewhere around successfully out of date propels. Worriers demand that the enormous divisions among rich and powerless will reliably be with us, in impact relations similarly as in bounty and pay. While cover public hopping can't occur inside current conceptualizations, endless dissimilarity is neither unavoidable nor agreeable. Likewise, it is guidance (but verifiably not in its present design) that might go about as driving force, with the humblest of individuals having the choice to 'learn' right out of weight and the most crushed sharing and getting a charge out of activities also with the most extraordinary.

Preparing: THE GREAT UNEQUALISER

Regardless the educate enlightenment brand names, tutoring systems stay furnished to giving steady work to fabricate the wealth of a couple, fitting people to the workplace, and actuating the sham thought of guidance as human resource adventure. Guidance, as eventually practiced, is the adversary of significant worth, paying little heed to voluminous courses of action and swarm political addresses regardless of what may be generally anticipated. At the brand name levels, assortment is incredible and dissimilarity hated. Before long, and in enlightening associations and cycles everywhere, categorisation and excusal are spilling over. While preparing (as discussed underneath) ought to nor be centered around nor assessed in term of 'significant worth', general organization rides enlightening associations worldwide and cuts across the institutional, social and recorded factors that prompted noxious socio-informative isolation.

Enlighteningly, we can't win the Information Campaign, nor indeed the Knowledge Battle, also the Wisdom War, with middle age weapons and an oppressive request system. We as a world have taken in an uncommon course of action from the financial and mechanical pulses of globalization up until this point and, assuming we think about those activities, have the major thoughts for the genuinely troublesome pulse of considering, creating and keeping a comprehensive enlightening development, required and enabled by our planned world system. Responses to the enlightening troubles of the Digital Age should be arranged and passed on in full cognizance of the totally new conditions, huge opportunities and probable dangers. At whatever point responded to genuinely, participative and creatively, Digitization offers an unmatched opportunity to audit lopsided characters.

Regardless, pre-stacked handheld laborers to which individuals may connect can vanquish this issue, even in far away settings. It is seen too that a bigger area of the planet fundamental and discretionary schools are without power, and that actually or daylight based worked PC structures may on occasion be open in the mean pulse. Impressively more hence, it is seen that, assuming such fundamental unfair insufficiencies are not tended to and helped, the world's secret issues will not at any point be settled. This might well have monetary legitimizations anyway the moral ones are rapidly evident – and informative coordinators can't do whatever it takes not to face such issues.

CONCLUSION

Digitisation-Based Education As Evaluation Nothing enlighteningly will anypulse be the comparable again. With Digitization, the world is so remarkably and significantly changed that out and out new educational systems are both imperative and possible. We examine comprehensive between connectedness being exemplified in the Global School; near recognize may be gotten from basically seeing a 5-year old out and out at home with a device containing a zillion events the computational power of the mightiest workspace at the turn of the thousand years.

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CLINICAL EFFICIENCY OF HEMOSTATIC DRUGS IN SIMULTANE SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN THE NOSE CAVITY

Vokhidov U.N.

Department Of Otorhinolaryngology Tashkent State Dental Institute, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: Among the local hemostatic agents that cause a decrease in vascular permeability and denaturation of proteins, accompanied by their transition to a solid state, a large group of inorganic metal compounds is distinguished.

As a hemostatic drug of local action, feracryl is used - an incomplete iron salt of polyacrylic acid with an iron content of 0.05 to 0.5%. Being an acidic polyelectrolyte, feracryl forms, in the pH range 2.9 - 4.0, water-insoluble polycomplexes with proteins of various origins, including blood plasma proteins. Feracryl is used in aqueous and alcoholic solutions in concentrations from 1 to 10%, as well as in the form of a patch (hemostatic).

KEYWORDS: Hemostatic agents, anterior tamponade, nasal bleeding.

INTRODUCTION

Material and methods

We examined 30 patients with combined pathologies of the nasal cavity, such as deviation of the nasal septum, vasomotor rhinitis, concha bullosa, who were hospitalized in the ENT department of the InViVo clinic in 2018-2021. All patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including the collection of complaints, examination of the ENT organs, endoscopy, and computed tomography. Taking into account the pathology of the nasal cavity, all patients underwent surgical interventions corresponding to the pathology of the nose. At the end of the procedure, one side of the nasal cavity was tamponed with a gauze pad, the other with standard Hemostatic Sponge material. Materials were placed in both nasal cavities in random order, and, for this reason, each patient was a control for himself. All patients were prescribed postoperative antibiotics (second-generation cephalosporin) for 10 days, as well as analgesic

therapy as needed. The hemostatic sponge was in situ for 2 weeks after surgery, without any intervention; thereafter, the dissolved nasal swabs were carefully removed with suction. Patients were not informed about which tamponade material was placed on each side. All patients were discharged one day after surgery without acute complications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The severity of all subjective symptoms decreased in the interval between each pair of time points, and continued to decrease until DPO 30. Discomfort points for obstruction of the nasal passages (in all cases, $p < 0.001$ on day 2, after 1 week, 2 weeks and 1 month), postnasal syndrome ($p = 0.004$ after 2 weeks and $p < 0.001$ after 1 month), rhinitis ($p = 0.018$ after 2 weeks and $p < 0.001$ after 1 month), and headache (in all cases, $p < 0.001$ on day 2, after 1 week, 2 weeks and 1 month) were significantly lower for the Hemostatic Sponge than for Spongostan (Fig. 2). The scores for pain assessment during nasal tamponade were significantly lower for Cutanplast than for Spongostan (in all cases, $p < 0.001$ on day 2, after 1 week, 2 weeks and 1 month).

The tampon residual continued to decline significantly between the time points until DPO 30. The tampon residual was significantly lower for the Hemostatic Sponge than for the gauze tamponade. Most of the tampons from the Hemostatic Sponge completely resolved by DPO 30, while more than 25%, on average.

Both patient groups underwent postoperative endoscopy at 1 week, 2 weeks, 1 month, 2, 3, and 6 months. A statistically significant difference was found at 2 weeks, 1, 2 and 3 months on the LKES, POSE, and DIP scales between gauze pad and Hemostatic sponge swabs. However, after 6 months, there was no significant difference on these scales between the groups.

There was no accidental loss of a single tampon, and no patient had postoperative bleeding that would require replacement of a tampon to stop it. There were no postoperative complications or adverse reactions in any of the groups.

CONCLUSION

The hemostatic sponge has been found to be more effective in stopping bleeding after nasal surgery. However, the Hemostatic Sponge material has shown clear advantages due to its unique composition and short clearance profile. The material for the tamponade of the Hemostatic Sponge was more convenient, caused less pain, dissolves earlier, provided faster wound healing, and was less expensive. For this reason, the Hemostatic Sponge may be a safer

and more beneficial collagen-based material for tamponade after nasal surgery in terms of effectiveness and cost-effectiveness.

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INFLUENCE OF NOSE TAMPONADE ON QUALITY OF LIFE IN THE EARLY POSTOPERATIVE PERIOD AFTER SEPTOPLASTY

Kwang Hyun Kim,

Professor, Dsc, Otorhinolaryngology And Head And Neck Surgery Department

Seoul National University, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: Surgical treatment is the only method for correcting a deviated nasal septum. Most of surgeons' complete surgery on the nasal septum with anterior tamponade of the nasal cavity, which is necessary to fix the osteomeotal reconstructed flap in the median position, as well as to prevent complications such as bleeding, hematoma in the early postoperative period, and the formation of synechiae between of wall in the nasal cavity. For tamponade, in most cases, gauze tampons soaked in anti-inflammatory ointment are used. Despite the good fixing effect, such a tamponade completely turns off the main functions of the nose for the entire period - respiratory, drainage, protective; there is no ventilation of the paranasal sinuses, ventilation of the middle ear is impaired. Tamponade causes compression of the injured mucous membrane, and, consequently, ischemia, up to perforation of the septum and pain (especially during removal), trauma to the mucous membrane, lacrimation, discomfort when swallowing, sleep disturbances, increased blood pressure, headache due to disturbed microcirculation in the vessels of the head brain, creates a good environment for the reproduction of a bacterial agent with a rarely occurring syndrome of infectious-toxic shock.

KEYWORDS: Quality of life, septoplasty, anterior tamponade.

INTRODUCTION

We used a collagen hemostatic sponge (TURON SILK PHARM, Uzbekistan, Tashkent), consisting of two active substances - collagen, prepared from the skin or tendons of cattle. When applied to the wound surface, the collagen hemostatic sponge polymerizes with the formation of an elastic fibrin film. This process repeats the main stages of the physiological process of blood

coagulation and allows you to stop diffuse bleeding, glue and fix tissues, and also accelerate wound healing. During the healing process, the formed clot of fibrin “glue” is completely absorbed. Collagen hemostatic sponge is metabolized in the same way as endogenous fibrin, due to fibrinolysis and phagocytosis. To prevent transmission of infection due to the use of drugs obtained from human blood or plasma, standard measures have been taken, namely: selection of donors, screening of harvested blood plasma for specific markers of infection and the inclusion of effective steps in the inactivation of viruses in production. The measures taken are effective against enveloped viruses such as HIV, hepatitis C and B. After thawing, the contents of two vials were placed in a dispensing device, a special tip was attached to the syringe for injecting the drug into hard-to-reach places. The drug is economical to use - 1-2 ml of glue is enough for one septoplasty. The glue was injected between the sheets of mucoperichondria and mucoperiosteum and pressed tightly, distributing it evenly along the entire length, after which the nasal cavity was tamponed on both sides with gauze tampons for 2-5 minutes (depending on the patient's presence of arterial hypertension and a tendency to bleeding) for uniform distribution and tighter adhesion of the mucous membranes. Then the tampons were removed, endoscopy of the nasal cavity was performed on both sides to visually confirm the tight adhesion of the mucous membrane with the reimplanted cartilage fragments, and only then the anesthesia was stopped.

The study from 2017 to 2019 involved 45 patients aged 19 to 40 years. Formed three groups of patients, 15 people each. The average age in the 1st group is 21.5 years, in the 2nd - 22.2 years, in the 3rd - 24.1 years. Of these, 19 (42.2%) are women and 26 (57.7%) are men.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comparative assessment of the quality of life of patients in the early postoperative period revealed the absence of statistically significant differences between the groups for all compared criteria, starting with C.5 ($p < 0.05$).

Evaluating the relationship with the anterior tamponade, which was used only in the 1st and 2nd groups, in determining the quality of life of patients, the presence of homogeneity of the 3rd group was revealed. Highly significant differences ($p < 0.01$) were determined between groups in C.1, 2 and 3 according to the criterion “drinking from a cup”, showing a higher quality of life in

patients of groups 1 and 3. The same was confirmed by significant differences ($p < 0.05$) according to the criterion "to sit in bed" at points 1 and 2, at the same control points there were highly significant statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$) according to the criterion "to get out of bed" and "nausea". When processing the data, highly significant differences ($p < 0.01$) in S. 1, 2, 3 and significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in S. 4 were determined according to the criteria of walking 10 m and walking 50 m ». In all four control points, highly significant differences ($p < 0.01$) were revealed according to the criteria of "physical pain" and "general weakness". According to the criterion "dizziness" in C.1 and 2 there were highly significant differences ($p < 0.01$), and at the point of difference between the groups, statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). According to all the studied criteria, a significant deterioration in the quality of life in the early postoperative period was determined in patients of the 2nd group in comparison with the 1st and 3rd groups.

CONCLUSIONS

The presence of anterior tamponade in the early postoperative period after septoplasty adversely affects the physical condition of patients, thereby reducing the quality of life. The use of a collagen hemostatic sponge is the most acceptable alternative, which allows to exclude the negative effect of the anterior nasal tamponade and to achieve tight adhesion of the septal mucosa sheets, as well as fixation between them of reimplanted and reconstructed bone and cartilaginous fragments, minimizing postoperative bleeding and hematomas of the nasal septum.

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METHOD OF IMPROVEMENT IN THE PROCESS OF STRETCHING NON-FERROUS METAL WIRE

Dr. Shuhrat N. Fayzimatov

Phd, Professor Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan

Boburbek A. Tojiyev

Assistant Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan

Sherali D. Jo'rayev

Master Student Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: Non-ferrous metals and their alloys are the main construction materials in the national economy, aviation, rocketry, electrical engineering and radio engineering. Non-ferrous metallurgy in Uzbekistan has been developing since the 1930s on the basis of local mineral resources. Non-ferrous, rare and precious metals (gold, copper, lead, zinc, tungsten, molybdenum, mercury, etc.) are presented in the country.

KEYWORDS: Non-ferrous metal, metal wire, non-ferrous metallurgy, elongation process, chemical process, improvement.

INTRODUCTION

The stretching process' efficiency is determined by increasing the load grade wire production costs while saving raw materials. This is accomplished by improving the technological process of cable product preparation and stretching while increasing product volume by increasing technological equipment productivity, forming equipment and component service life, reducing material waste, and increasing the machine tool's useful working vector.

1-picture. Stretch bench control system.

Due to the slide, the wires are now stretched on VSK-13 looms, which are one of the most important looms for wire stretching. This workbench's technological features are as follows: The diameter of the stretched Wire is 7,2-8 mm; the diameter of the finished Wire is 1-2,7 mm; the number of voloks is 7-13; the stretching speed is 10-30 M/s; the number of pulling rollers is 7; the diameter of the pulling Shears is 133-225; the total mass of the workpiece is 13870 kg; the dimensions of the workpiece are L-5,72 m, 353-343 M2.

2-picture. General view of the VSK-13 bench. 1-wire stretching chamber; 2-allowing drum; 3-guiding roller; 4-pulling rollers; 5-special pushing roller; 6-guiding roller; 7-condenser; 8 - controlling device; 9-receiving drum; 10-fil'yeraz;

The VSK-13 machine is designed to stretch wires with diameters ranging from 1 mm to 2,7 mm, as well as an oxygen-free copper cathode stretching with an 8 mm diameter. The VSK-13 bench appears to be two-sided. Copper wire stretching machine with a solid look;

1. Wire stretching camera – this camera is made up of six bandages that are parallel to each other. These bandages are made up of Paws, which have a geometrical shape of a cone, as well as holding devices for elephants, which are one of the primary tools in the stretching chamber. The workbench's name comes from the fact that there are 13 of these devices. The Wire is wrapped in a bandage on the lowest leg at first, and as the diameter lowers, it is rolled into the middle and upper leg. This procedure is carried out without the involvement of an emulsion liquid. The purpose of this liquid is to cool the heated bandages in the process of stretching and the elephants carrying out the process of stretching the wire is used to facilitate the movement of wire under such bandages, after the wire of a certain diameter is released, which is required from the stretching chamber, this wire is pulled using a wire puller. If a soft wire is required, the drawer will be given to the heating (OTJIG) device once the sheepskin is removed.

2. Transmitter drum—this drum's job is to provide direction to the stretching chamber of a stretched wire of a specific diameter.

3. Condenser – when the speed of the receiving device [vt, vq] is higher, this device fulfills the function of raising the speed of the receiving device. The compensator has been raised. If the speed of both devices is normal, the condenser is in the middle. The Wire is dragged into the drum device after passing through the condenser.

4. Receiving device—this device has its own engine and moves around on its own. A firm movement is performed by the device's drum.

The expansion to the Awazi improved the VSK-13 bench by allowing for the collection of object data on the process's continuity, wire quality, composition homogeneity, and the absence of non-material.

Figure 1 shows the taximization of the VSK-13 bench's working vector in one shift. Here, the maximum length of the stretch bench's stop arm is equal to 43 percent of the equipment's filling, connecting with the replacement of the divided volok by weight and using the elimination

of interruptions, so that the filer's service life is extended and the option of increasing the stretch bench's productivity is available.

The method of improving the stretching machine and adapting it to the technological process is considered in this variant, and the practical results of its implementation are presented with the definition of the physical model of the system "stretching machine+additional pulling drum," as well as the technical and economic indicators of the stretching machine improvement with the installation of an additional pulling drum.

Production of cable The goal of developing a method for raising the resource-saving max of stretching equipment by extending the service life of the volok is to increase the quality of the completed product in a single unit while increasing production efficiency.

The following is the kiln system that we presented in the technique of upgrading the stretching machine tool (Figure 3): 1 - giver; 2 - loom; 3 - fillers; 4-6 - retracting Drums; 5 - clean filera; 7 - electro-engine; 8 - encoder(reverse connection); 9 - cable-killing device; 10 - gauge of diameter; 11 - additional pulling drum; 13 - copper wire; 14 – simulator.

A clean (diamond) voloka allows to increase the service life by an average of 15% as a result of the improvement work carried out during the studies, but its price in this instance is up to 250 euros per unit, whereas the cost of Kattic cotishmeli filers is up to 84 euros per unit.

3-picture. Scheme of the technique of improving the stretching bench

4-picture. Productivity analysis of the stretching bench.

All this made it possible to conduct a comparative analysis of the impact of stretching technologies on the object of stretching (Table 1).

The following accounting information on the technical and economic indicators of improvement was obtained.

Table 1

Name of the parameter	Improvement -until the resurrection	After improvement	
		Filer service life increase, 10%	Filer service life increase, 15%
Machine power meter, clock	20	22	23
The amount of working shifts	8	2,7	2,9
Productivity, shift / km	5 000	5 500	5 750
Productivity, year / km	1 523 000	1 675 300	1 738 800

The proposed findings were based on the enhancement of existing stretching technology by adding more stretching blocks to the takcoslage and stretching bench, which improved the stretching process' efficiency and reduced the cost of increasing the diamond filer's working life. The recommended kilo approach enables for the rapid development of various stretching machines by making minor structural changes in a short amount of time.

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ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE ACTIVITIES OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Javlon B. Bakhodirov

Lecturer Department of Constitutional law Tashkent State University of Law, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: At the moment, we can talk about a very large number of functions, tasks and powers of the prosecutor's office. Developing as a separate system in the mechanism of the state, the Prosecutor's office is endowed with the rights both to conduct an investigation and to act as a party to the prosecution in court, and is endowed with issues of support for citizens and organizations in civil and economic courts. Also, the Prosecutor's office is not deprived of a law-making function, where the Prosecutor General can take an active legislative initiative. In this research work all above are studied.

KEYWORDS: Prosecutor's office, presecution, economic courts, execution

INTRODUCTION

Optimization of the activity of the Prosecutor's office is a set of organizational and legal measures aimed at improving the activities of the prosecutor's office, exemption from unnecessary and unnecessary functions.

At the moment, we can talk about a very large number of functions, tasks and powers of the prosecutor's office. Developing as a separate system in the mechanism of the state, the Prosecutor's office is endowed with the rights both to conduct an investigation and to act as a party to the prosecution in court, and is endowed with issues of support for citizens and organizations in civil and economic courts. Also, the Prosecutor's office is not deprived of a law-making function, where the Prosecutor General can take an active legislative initiative. However, despite such a number of functions, the activities of the prosecutor's office in many respects

remain not systematized from a legal point of view, and therefore there is a need to optimize it, i.e. simplify and direct it to a more practical course of work.

The focus of the Prosecutor's Office on the comprehensive implementation of activities to protect the national state interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rule of law and the rule of law presupposes the inclusion in its sphere, in addition to the function of supervision over the execution of laws, all other functions of the prosecutor's office. At the same time, the most intensive burden of the prosecutor's office falls on the implementation of the functions of criminal prosecution, coordination, international cooperation, participation in law-making activities.

The inclusion in the sphere of activity of the Prosecutor's office for the protection of national state interests of the function of coordinating the activities of law enforcement agencies seems to be absolutely necessary due to the high urgency of consolidating their efforts to combat the most dangerous forms of encroachment on these interests. [1]

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

It is necessary to ensure a comprehensive approach in the fight against offenses and, first of all, crimes. With regard to prosecutorial supervision of the execution of laws, an integrated approach can mean: comprehensive, purposeful and active use by the prosecutor of all legal means at his disposal; coordination of supervision in the area under consideration with other branches of prosecutorial supervision and all participants in the activities of the prosecutor's office; close linking of supervisory work with preventive activities; constant and close interaction of prosecutors with representative and executive authorities, law enforcement, regulatory and other bodies, as well as with public formations on strengthening the rule of law; linking supervisory measures with the most important socio-economic, environmental and other tasks being solved in the region (district, city, region).

The achievement of an integrated approach can also be facilitated by: close linking of supervisory activities with preliminary investigation in criminal cases and, in particular, conducting prosecutor's inspections simultaneously with the preliminary investigation; conducting joint inspections with control bodies and other bodies; active exercise by the prosecutor of the right to instruct law enforcement, regulatory and other bodies to conduct inspections. Thus, we are talking about creating a single, well-coordinated front for the fight against offenders.

The increase in the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision over the execution of laws is associated with the improvement of the management (management) of supervisory activities by higher prosecutor's offices.

It can go in the following directions:

- timely, prompt correction of supervisory activities, aiming it at solving the main, key tasks of strengthening the rule of law, preventing offenses;
- improvement of the analysis of supervisory activities and timely communication of the results of the analysis to lower-level prosecutors;
- timely adoption of measures to eliminate errors and omissions in the work committed by lower-level prosecutors;
- improvement of methodological assistance to lower-level prosecutors;
- preparation of more advanced methodological manuals, developments, instructions, letters and provision of prosecutors with them;
- improving the dissemination of positive work experience;
- improvement of control over the introduction into practice of the latest achievements of science and practice, advanced methods and techniques for detecting and eliminating offenses;
- development of initiative, independence and combativeness among lower-level prosecutors. At the same time, the main efforts should be directed to providing effective assistance to prosecutors of districts and cities in organizing prosecutorial supervision of the execution of laws on a scientific basis.

In terms of improving the methodological skills of low-level prosecutors, good results can be obtained by employees of regional and equal prosecutor's offices conducting demonstration (training) inspections of the implementation of laws. We are talking about training in the conditions of a real test.

The next direction is the improvement of tactics and methods for detecting violations of laws and establishing the circumstances that contribute to them. First of all, it is necessary to improve the quality of prosecutor's checks, which, unfortunately, is not always high.

Prosecutors do not always prepare for inspections, as a result of which they are sometimes conducted superficially and violations of laws are not detected, the circumstances contributing

to violations are not established. The elimination of these and other shortcomings will contribute to improving the quality of prosecutor's checks.

This can also contribute to:

- complex application of various verification actions by prosecutors;
- the use of various techniques and methods, including forensic;
- active involvement of specialists in inspections;
- conducting inspections jointly (simultaneously) with other law enforcement agencies, regulatory and other bodies;
- conducting complex inspections, i.e. inspections of the implementation of several laws. In addition, the improvement of the current and the development of new private methods of conducting inspections will contribute to improving the quality of inspections.

Improving the practice of prosecutors' response to violations of laws can also contribute to improving the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of laws.

Improvement of the response practice can go in the following directions •

- improvement of the procedure for introducing acts of prosecutorial supervision, active use of all legal means and acts of response;
- combination of written and oral forms of response;
- increasing the acuteness of the prosecutor's response;
- improving the structure and quality of the acts of prosecutorial supervision;
- strengthening of control by prosecutors over the implementation of the submitted response acts;
- systematic generalization (analysis) of response practices;
- improving the professional skills of prosecutors. All forms of professional development of prosecutors can contribute to this.

In addition, further improvement of the legislation regulating the organization and activities of the prosecutor's office, as will be discussed in the next paragraph of this chapter, can contribute to improving the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision, as well as all the multifaceted activities of the prosecutor's office. It is clear that the improvement of the entire legislative array of Russia and, in particular, the elimination of gaps in the legal regulation of certain public relations, discrepancies, duplication, and its codification will ultimately contribute to improving the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision of the execution of laws.

Prosecutors should use all the means (opportunities) at their disposal to increase the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision over the execution of laws, which will undoubtedly contribute to strengthening the rule of law and the rule of law both in the regions and in the country as a whole.

In order to strengthen the legal mechanisms for protecting the rights and interests of business entities, ensuring guarantees of legality in their activities, improving the investment climate and business environment in the republic, as well as optimizing the activities of the prosecutor's office by eliminating tasks and functions unusual for them, the following was established from April 1, 2019:

- coordination of inspections of the activities of business entities and control over the legality of their conduct by regulatory bodies are carried out by the Commissioner under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities (hereinafter - the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs);
- decisions of the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs regarding the conduct of inspections of the activities of business entities are mandatory for the regulatory authorities;
- The Chamber of Commerce and Industry participates in ensuring the activities of the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs in the field of coordinating inspections of the activities of business entities by exercising public control over the legality of inspections in the activities of business entities conducted by regulatory authorities.

It should be noted that in the exercise of his powers, the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs:

- monitors compliance by regulatory authorities with the requirements of legislation in the field of inspections of the activities of business entities;
- considers and studies the validity of requests from regulatory authorities to conduct inspections of the activities of business entities;
- makes decisions on the permission or refusal to conduct inspections of the activities of business entities, as well as the extension or postponement of their deadlines;
- takes measures to bring to justice the guilty officials of regulatory authorities for violating legislation in the field of conducting inspections of the activities of business entities, etc. [2]

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree "On measures to radically improve the system of business protection and optimize the activities of the Prosecutor's Office."

According to the document, from April 1, 2019:

- coordination of inspections of the activities of business entities and control over the legality of their conduct by regulatory authorities are carried out by the Presidential Commissioner for the Protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities;
- Decisions of the Commissioner for the protection of the rights of entrepreneurs regarding the conduct of inspections of the activities of business entities are mandatory for the regulatory authorities;
- The Chamber of Commerce and Industry participates in ensuring the activities of the Commissioner for the protection of the rights of entrepreneurs in the field of coordinating inspections of the activities of business entities by exercising public control over the legality of inspections in the activities of business entities conducted by regulatory authorities. [3]

CONCLUSION

The unified system of electronic registration of inspections is transferred from the jurisdiction of the Prosecutor General's Office to the jurisdiction of the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs.

In the system of the Prosecutor's Office of Uzbekistan, the following are abolished:

- two units of positions of Deputy Prosecutor General;
- Department for Legal Protection of Entrepreneurship and Investments of the Prosecutor General's Office;
- the Department for supervision of the execution of decisions of the President of the Prosecutor General's Office and its territorial departments;
- the Department for Supervision of the implementation of legislation in the field of tax and customs reforms of the Prosecutor General's Office and its territorial departments and other positions. [4]

The Inspection for the control of the agro-industrial complex and ensuring food Security is transferred to the jurisdiction of the Cabinet of Ministers, while maintaining the current funding procedure. The Agency will be transformed into the Inspection for the Control of the Agro-Industrial Complex under the Cabinet of Ministers.

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THE ISSUE OF SUSTENANCE AND PROFESSION IN HAKIM TERMIZI'S WORK "BAYANUL KASB" ("DESCRIPTION OF THE PROFESSION")

Lazizbek A. Xaitov

Phd Student, Department Of History And Source Study Of Islam And Philosophy Bukhara State
University, Bukhara City, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: This article analyzes Hakim Termizi's ideas about the concept of the profession and sustenance in his work "Bayanul kasb" ("Description of the profession")

KEYWORDS: Hakim Termizi, "Bayanul kasb", sufism, occupation, sustenance, labor, honesty and purity.

INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of mystical and philosophical teachings, special attention has always been paid to the issue of the profession. The issue of profession and sustenance have been one of the topics that has caused a lot of controversy among Muslims. These two concepts are closely related. The increase in sustenance is dialectically connected with occupation and labor. The sustenance of professional, honest workers will increase. The concept of rizq (sustenance/provision) is the key to standardizing the concepts of food and profession.

DISCUSSION

In sufism, the relationship between the sustenance and profession can be described as follows:

1. Put your trust in Allah, and it is He who will provide for you. Proponents of this idea apply the idea that one should only pray, and not be engaged in any occupation.
2. Work, act, and put your trust in God. Proponents of this idea believe that Allah provides sustenance, but it is necessary to work and work honestly.
3. All you have to do is work, and if you run, your food will increase. That is, they follow the idea that you will only find your sustenance.

Hakim Termizi's attitude to the concepts of the profession and sustenance is described in his work "Bayanul kasb" ("Description of the profession"). The written work deals with national and universal values, such as the qualities of being enlightened, acquiring a certain profession, earning a living through honest work, earning a living by one's own labor. In covering the subject of Sufism, he cites many verses and hadiths from the verses of the Qur'an and the Hadiths, as well as real-life examples and parables to better explain the subject.

In the Sufi book Bayanul Kasb (Description of the profession), the word for profession and salary was initially coined by the first man, Adam (PBUH). He is remembered as a man who was the first to be called to demand a food." In the example of a verse from Surat al-Taha, the Qur'an states that Adam was given four things in Paradise: food, drink, clothing and shelter. [1:326]. The difficulty of seeking sustenance was made obligatory to Adam a.s. (on the ground) as Adam a.s. relinquished the obedience, as a result he demanded for provision. Hakim Termezi concludes that "whoever is more obedient to his Lord, his sustenance will be easier." [2:116]

Hakim Termizi in his work "Bayanul kasb": one of the first in history to emphasize that a woman's pension is obligatory on the land. [3:367] Pensions in the annotated dictionary means "allocating money for good". The Shari'ah says, "Provide one's dependents with adequate clothing, food, cleanliness, and household utensils." Pension is obligatory through marriage and kinship. The fact that alimony is obligatory has been established by the Qur'an, the Sunnah, ijma' and reason. Hence, the sustenance consists of the four things mentioned above, such as food, drink, clothing, and shelter.

Hakim Termezi talked about those who would be provided without any demand. Here the first group is called the Siddiqs, and as their representative they mention our mother Mary(PBUH). The spontaneous supply of sustenance to the sinners may have been to confirm their sincerity. In fact, they were just like everyone else, earning a living. In particular, our mother Mary(PBUH) was one of those who demanded a salary, she was engaged in spinning, and Jesus (PBUH) used to earn a living from this profession.

Hakim Termezi's attitude towards halal food and his profession later influenced Bahauddin Naqshbandi, the founder of the Naqshbandi school of thoughts. was the basis for the formation of the principle. Bahauddin Naqshband paid special attention to labor and craft. He first asked the children who came in search of knowledge, "What profession do you know?" He

encouraged those who did not know any professions to take up a profession and then study the Islamic science. He wrote about it

Денгиздан ҳамиша изламагил дур,
Одамга бир ҳунар бас, эзгу турар [4:34].
Don't always look for the sea,
A profession is good for a person

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Hakim Termizi's ideas on the sustenance and profession are based on the pamphlet *Bayanul Profession (Description of the Profession)*. The doctrine of “Hakimiyya”, founded by Hakim Termezi, correctly understood the concept of a profession, provision, and engaged in honest work and professionalism.

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INSTRUCTIVE PROGRAM VARIETY IN COMPLETE TUTORING

Pooja Mishra

Branch Of Education Students Of Integrated B.Ed _ M.Ed Rajendra (Autonomous) College,
Balangir, Odisha, India

ABSTRACT: Complete tutoring is portrayed as a learning environment that advances full near and dear, academic and capable improvement of all understudies in any case race, class, concealing, sex, handicap, learning style and language. The instructive program addresses an essential gadget for empowering an extended thought of far reaching preparing. In this manner complete instructive program improvement should be seen as a tenacious cycle and immovably laced with social thought. The standard goal of this assessment is to investigate social occasion of good practices in the variety of the instructive program for the exhaustive tutoring. In the made report out of NCF 2005, it is clearly referred to that the school should welcome contrastingly proficient children, young women, minorities, youths from poor monetary culture, kids from limited portion similarly as children from different conditions who ought to be benefitted via preparing.

KEYWORDS: Curricular change, instructive program, complete guidance, finding, NCF, UDL.

INTRODUCTION

The child with insufficiency is one who diverges intellectually, really, socially, or genuinely so especially dependent on what is considered to be common turn of events and improvement that he can't get most outrageous benefit by a standard school program and requires an exceptional class or invaluable rules or organization. The different sorts of available informational tasks for the youths with failures are separated (Special) preparing, joined tutoring and complete guidance. So Inclusive guidance is the plan of organizations to understudies with failures in their neighborhood schools with fundamental assistance

organizations and significant aides for youngsters and teachers. It is a structure wherein all children from a given neighborhood together in a comparative close by school fusing young people with learning inconveniences, exceptional prerequisites or failures. Plan for such a sort of preparing shows a vibe of confidence in the minds of impaired children and offers them permission to the legitimate course of action of tutoring. Extensive is a work to guarantee that the understudies with inadequacies go to class close by their associates and neighbors while also getting whatever "uncommonly arranged direction and support" they need to achieve raised assumptions and win as understudies.

The possibility of far reaching preparing has been spelt out in the Salamanca clarification and the framework for movement on outstanding necessities guidance 1994. It communicates that all organizations have been approached to "embrace as an issue of law or methodology, the rule of thorough guidance, enrolling all children in standard schools with the exception of assuming there are persuading clarifications behind doing regardless." The fundamental assurance is that the school should meet the informative necessities of all young people paying little mind to their failures or obstructions.

Principles of complete guidance

- The public authority financed instructive framework is the foundation for exhaustive tutoring.
- Inclusive tutoring at all levels benefits understudies with phenomenal necessities and their associates.
- Each understudy is stand-out and necessities an individualized method for managing guidance to meet their savvy individual, physical, social and their partners.
- The understudy's viewpoints are fixed on and focused on.
- Individual differences between understudies are a wellspring of luxuriousness and assortment and not an issue.
- Inclusive guidance gives identical benefits to all.

As discussed above instructive arrangement should reliably be dynamic to meet the issues of the understudies. Consequently, it should be managed suddenly. In any case, instructive program headway should be seen at an advancing, powerful cycle, reliably be in a state of organized changes. Second, the pattern of instructive arrangement setup should be adaptable and material to different subjects and conditions. Finally, the teacher should have a fundamental

occupation in the arrangement cycle. They should not be relegated to a helper circumstance in distinctive fitting instructive arrangement for their understudies.

Instructive arrangement adaption is a persistent remarkable cycle that changes and changes the prescribed program of studies to meet the learning essentials of an understudy with uncommon necessities. Variety, offices and, adjustments might seem like tradable terms, yet with respect to thought they pass on basically special importance accommodation and changes fill in as two separate kinds of curricular changes. It enables the educating gathering to welcome understudies, in light of everything, and ensures that each understudy is tried to learn. Instructive program change is needed in each part in the understudy's day. Learning, socialization, independence and prosperity are ensured for the understudies when all school staffs are familiar their appearance parts in the homeroom similarly as in the passageways, library, rec focus, wilderness exercise center and dispatch room, etc Educational arrangement change reliably requires guidance partner maintain.

These fuses the 3 critical principles/rules, for instance, starting one is Engagement: which is for purposeful, moved understudies, animate income and motivation for learning, Second one is Representation: for inventive, capable understudies, present information and substance surprisingly, Third one is Action and Expression: For key, objective – composed understudies, separate the habits in which that understudies can convey what they realize similarly as reflecting assortment in teaching and supporting the social value targets of individual instructors. So it is to improve and upgrade instructing and learning for all people reliant upon legitimate encounters in to how individuals learn. It endorses in new advancements and electronic contraptions and give one more viewpoint on with failures.

CONCLUSION

Far reaching preparing is a devouring issue towards showing the children with insufficiency and learning issues with the average children, the instructive arrangement ought to be laid out in such a way which should resolve the issues of expanded region if understudies. While illustrating the instructive program the technique makers should unmark, the fitting age, premium, mind

research similarly as the prerequisites of the particular culture. The instructive program should spread worth all through the informative system where all the challenged person understudies perceive their covered gifts and sharpen their musings, contemplations to rule in their life. Taking everything into account, an inspiring mentality of the overall population similarly as instructors helps for the productive execution of instructive arrangement.

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ACTUAL DISPARITY OF MANDIBLE IMPRESSION ANTRUM ON REGULATE TOPOGRAPHIC BETWEEN SUDANESE PEOPLE

Sadiq Ibrahim

Life Systems Division, Faculty Of Medicine, The National Ribat University Khartoum, Sudan
Anatomy Office, Faculty Of Medicine, The National Ribat University Khartoum, Sudan

ABSTRACT: Establishment: the mandible sinus assortments are essential between peoples. These assortments might interface with provocative afflictions like sinusitis or various diseases (ominously helpless rhino-sinusitis and bronchial asthma). **Aim:** The place of this assessment was to investigate mandible sinus assortments by using CT pictures in adult Sudanese people. **Methods:** This was observational illustrative cross sectional examination coordinated in Khartoum state-Sudan from June to Dec 2014. The assessment was done in 30 volunteers. All individuals went through head CT channels and sagittal and coronal cuts were gained.

KEYWORDS: Mandible, Sinus, Physical assortments, Sudanese.

INTRODUCTION

Paranasal sinus life frameworks and assortments have obtained interest with the introduction of utilitarian endoscopic sinus operation and the possibility of the ostiomeatal complex [1]. The mandible sinus is the space inside the body of the maxilla, alluded to in earlier days as the mandible antrum. The sinus is pyramidal perfectly healthy, the base at the flat mass of the nose and the apex in the zygomatic pattern of the maxilla. The highest point of the sinus is the floor of the circle. The floor of the sinus is the alveolar part (tooth-bearing zone) of the maxilla. Front and back dividers are the relating dividers of the maxilla. Certain edges appear inside the cavity; a consistent one is at the convergence of roof and front divider, made by the sliding passage of the infraorbital nerve with in its canal[2]. The mandible sinus is accessible after entering the world, yet is near a shallow cut, fimpressionly clogged into a short culde-sac anteriorly and

posteriorly. It uncovers the even mass of the nose, under the middle concha, and lies just under the normal side of the floor of the circle. The body of the neonatal maxilla flat to this is stacked with making teeth. The sinus changes in size; a colossal one might loosen up into the zygomatic pattern of the maxilla and into the alveolar cycle so the establishments of the three molar teeth (and maybe of the premolars also) lie immediately under the floor or undertaking into it. The ostium of the sinus is high up and well back on its nasal divider. It is 2-4 mm in estimation. (A second more humble ostium routinely lies posteriorly.) It opens at the back finish of the semilunar rest in the middle meatus of the sidelong mass of the nose. An accurate data on the existence frameworks of the paranasal antrum is principal for the clinician.

one of these assortments is mandible antrum septa and they are slight dividers of cortical bone present inside the mandible sinus, with variable number, thickness and length. Such septa may seclude the sinus into no less than two pits arising out of the second rate and equal dividers of the sinus. Septa beginning from teeth may be requested by their headway at the different times of the dental emanation. Another assortment is additional mandible ostia they are generally single, yet on occasion may be unique. Such assortment may be innate or discretionary to sinus diseases.

METHODS

This was observational expressive cross sectional assessment coordinated in Khartoum state-Sudan from June to Dec 2014. The assessment was done in 30 volunteers later formal made consent insisted by the local moral board. All individuals went through head CT checks and sagittal and coronal cuts were gotten. Individuals were sound individuals without history of head or face injury or sinus movement history.

RESULTS

Actual assortments, in relationship with their natural conditions, were found to be peril factors for some respiratory parcel hypochondriac conditions. Consequently, recognizing these assortments has actually been fundamental for clinical practice. Paranasal sinus life frameworks

and assortments have procured interest with the introduction of utilitarian endoscopic sinus operation and the data on actual assortments is by and large huge in the cautious organization and expressly in the evasion of entrapments. The obtainment of an extraordinary significance of the sinus life frameworks for a preoperative endoscopic appraisal ought to be conceivable by strategies for figured tomographic that is the best quality level in the examination of such designs, for giving exact information on sensitive tissues, bone constructions and impression, thusly portraying an extraordinarily tricky imaging.

DISCUSSION

Discussion as for the ordinariness and clinical giganticness of mandible sinus hard anatomic assortments and mucosal inconsistencies is consolidated as a manual for help the otolaryngologist, radiologist and maxillofacial experts in the appraisal of coronal sinus CT channels procedure.

CONCLUSION

Assortments of mandible sinus underline how critical it is for the dentomaxillofacial radiologist, otolaryngologists, radiologist and anatomists to be aware of the actual assortments of the mandible antrum. Actual assortments of mandible impression antrum are typical and may be a slanting variable for sinus and upper respiratory plot afflictions. Examinations of these assortments and inconsistency from the standard were done in various countries worldwide yet no assessments were done between Sudanese. This assessment addresses a data base with regards to mandible sinus in Sudan. Further assessments are required including gigantic model number for greater appraisal and examination.

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ORDINARINESS AND RISK FACTORS OF INHALE AMIDST OPTIONAL SCHOOL FEMALE UNDERSTUDIES IN ARAR

Mai Yamani

Family And Community Medicine Dept., Psmmc, Riyadh, Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT: Show: Inhale is the really overall justification for preventable passings. Studies have exhibited that inhale beginning during youth works on the likelihood of continued inhale during adulthood and lessens the chance of halting. Various past investigates have been coordinated in different areas of Saudi Arabia to perceive the inescapability of inhale amidst folks; scarcely any assessments recalled females for different region anyway no examinations have been driven amidst female at northern line of KSA. This assessment intended to choosing the normality of inhale and recognize peril factors amidst optional school female understudies in Arar, KSA 2018.

KEYWORDS: Inhale inescapability, female, young woman, optional school understudies, Arar, Saudi Arabia.

INTRODUCTION

Tobacco inhale is one of the best broad clinical issues on earth with more than 6 million passings consistently as eventual outcome of direct tobacco use and around 890 000 passings each year as result of non-smokers being introduced to reused smoke . WHO assesses that 80% of the world's 1.1 billion smokers live in low-and focus pay countries . Regardless, in non-modern countries, tobacco use continues to extend by around 3.4% consistently. Tobacco use is the vitally overall justification for preventable Deaths. Like the fundamental peril component of unforeseen passing in folks and second in females amidst normal age.

The ordinariness of inhale differentiated from region to one more as they observed that Aljwaf, Northen Borders regions have the most raised power while the least inescapability was found from adults who live in Aseer Jizan and Albaha. In Hail, an assessment by Algorinees et al. To

assess the inescapability of inhale amidst the male discretionary school understudies saw that as 19.5% of understudies were current smokers. In that survey, 79% of the smokers uncovered that they started inhale since they imitated the adult. Likewise 27% of smoker individuals uncovered that their families understand that they smoke.

Data variety gadget: Self-controlled survey was used in the assessment was in Arabic language under overseer maker in missing of teachers to keep up hidden. The overview included 18 Variables from which is a Global Standard School-Based (GYTS) for purposely checking tobacco use amidst youth and following key tobacco control pointers, It consolidates 56 requests arranged, certain requests decided to cover the objective of this assessment.

Accordingly, in this assessment, we intended to perceive the ordinariness of inhale amidst the female optional school understudies in Arar developed 14 to 17 years and it was found that 19.2% of the individuals were smokers. The disclosures of our assessment are in close concurrences with results from in advance thinks about which reported that in Hail the inescapability of inhale was 19.5%. Notwithstanding the way that the examination was done particularly amidst folks, similarities can be drawn between the two metropolitan regions both arranged in the north and proposition near friendly, and monetary factors .

It is at this point thought to be truly possible that the inescapability of inhale when differentiated and various assessments was done in various spaces of Saudi Arabia amidst adolescent and this may be a direct result of different sexual direction this might accept standard occupation in the unmistakable between result add to this squeezing factor from social, culture and severe component and as we presumably know Saudi is conservative society. Our results propose the most grounded variable to begin inhale was related to mates and a couple of relatives smokers at home other than gatekeepers. The sidekick pressure was moreover recognized to contribute essentially in making the decision of being a smoker which is unsurprising with various examinations, for instance, that finished in Jeddah which suggested that one of the affecting component is level of tutoring of gatekeepers [4] . Moreover, as in National Guard area in Riyadh recommending that one of the rule factor is having accessible time and easing from pressure [5] . Besides, over piece of the smoker individuals tried to quit inhale if post-inhale assistance was agreed to them reasonably. There were a couple of

limitations at any rate in our examination. Our survey was particularly amidst female understudies, this may in future urge specialists to do concentrates amidst male understudies as well.

CONCLUSION

We really want to grow level of Awareness similarly as, inhale suspension programs composed the youngsters are fundamentally needed in this region. As in this examination show the fundamental age to start inhale is at 16-17 years and more prepared an enormous piece of them on assessment 11, so it ought to incite the prosperity preparing to start illuminating with regards to the horrendous contacts concerning inhale in center school classes.

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CONSEQUENCES OF SWAMP WEATHER ON CARTILAGE ALLEVIATE

Aydin Tanyel

Branch Of Oral And Maxillofacial Surgery, Faculty Of Dentistry, Istanbul University, Istanbul,
Turkey

ABSTRACT: Saline water framework is by and large used for the balance of the glow age during osteotomy. Reason: The inspiration driving this examination was to evaluate the effect of the saline water framework environment on cartilage patching. Material and Method: Standardized exhausting and miniscrew position was acted in the tibias of 18 Sprague Dawley rodents with turning thistle uncooled, cooled with 25°C and 4°C saline water frameworks. Later the 21 days, the differentiation in recovering was seen between the uncooled and cooled social events. Results: Although there was no quantifiably basic qualification between the social affair overwhelmed with 25°C and 4°C saline for as of late cartilage course of action, osteoblasts were seen more powerful and cartilage marrow was more novel in get-together 4°C than pack 25°C. There is no shortcoming to use 25°C, but it very well may be more astute to use 4°C for quick retouching.

KEYWORDS: Cartilage retouching, saline water framework environment.

INTRODUCTION

Dental implantation and fixation of screws in any capacity whatsoever are performed by exhausting the cartilage and the accomplishment of these undertakings depend upon various parts. Through these components, warm injuries happening on account of environment raise during exhausting, may be the most influent one. The edge level for warm injuries on the cartilage is the 47°C momentarily and the environment can raise that level successfully during entering by rotational thistles. As a result of warm injury, cartilage isn't recently resorbed at this point also replaced with fat cells. Likewise, the mechanical plan of the cartilage is cripple. To

keep the cartilage from the environment raise during infiltrating, distinctive water framework systems are used and by and large, clean saline game plans are the material of choice (6,7). In spite of the way that, taking everything into account, there is positively not an intelligent data in the composition, there is a conviction among the experts that cooled saline water framework is more fruitful than the uncooled saline water framework to protect the cartilage from the warm injuries. The justification behind the momentum assessment was to investigate the effect of the water framework environment on the cartilage patching. For this point, standardized exhausting and miniscrew position was acted in the tibias of 18 Sprague Dawley rodents with turning unit uncooled, cooled with 25°C and 4°C saline water framework. The cartilage retouching was surveyed between the uncooled and cooled social events. Material and Method Experiments were planned to choose the effect of water framework environment on the cartilage later osteotomy and miniscrew position. For this point 3 months old weighing around 350 to 450 g 18 Sprague–Dawley rodents were kept up at 22 ±0.5 °C on a 12-h light/12-h faint cycle with free permission to water and standardized food in organism free separate pens. The total of the investigations were performed at the Istanbul University, Institutes of Experimental Science Laboratories (Istanbul, Turkey). Backing and all preliminary techniques performed were totally according to guidelines set up by the current regulative demonstrations and supported by the University Institutional Animal Welfare Committee.

Close to the completion of three weeks, animals were executed and right femurs of them were accumulated. By then, the models were sent off the pathology research focus (Istanbul University, Institute of Oncology, Department of Pathology, Istanbul, TURKEY) for the histopathological evaluation. The cutting line was started relating to the get over center of femurs at around 4 mm isolated from femoral heads, where the super opening arranging was made. The models were fixed in 10% formalin for multi week and decalcified in 10% formic destructive course of action (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) for 25 days. The decalcified models were embedded in paraffin and cut into 3 µm thick regions on charged slides using a microtome (Leica Microsystemic RM 2125, Germany), and routine hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was performed. The regions were reviewed with a light amplifying focal point (Olympus BX60 amplifying instrument) affixed to a high level camera (Olympus E-330) which related with a PC. A histomorphological review was performed by a singular dazed oral pathologist to evaluate the

presence of illness, rottenness, fibrosis and new cartilage game plan. All screw opening natural elements were surveyed by histopathologically with light amplifying focal point under 20, 40, 100 and 200x enhancements.

RESULTS

In this investigation, the aggregate of the quantifiable appraisals were performed by using the NCSS programming (NCSS Inc., 2007, USA). Ki-square and Fisher tests were performed for the evaluation of the total verifiable systems and besides abstract snippets of data. Probabilities of under 0.05 were seen as enormous ($p < 0,05$).

DISCUSSION

The environment climb on the cartilage during osteotomies performed by rotational systems is impacted by various factors. A part of these parts are cartilage thickness, and the space of the osteotomy, explicitly the proportion of cortical versus cancellous cartilage, which may be powerful. Other huge parts connect with the infiltrating, including the speed at which the drill turns, the sharpness of the edges on the drill, the thickness of the drill, and the power with which the drills applied where it counts. In any case the reason behind, this environment rise can cause damage or impaired recovering on the cartilage. As of late referred to, the recognized edge level that is required for the warm injury on the cartilage is 47°C for a period of 1 second.

For the security of the cartilage from the warm mischief during osteotomy, saline course of action is consistently applied to the drill and the osteotomy site in cautious practice. What's more moreover, most of the experts favor cool saline game plans and they acknowledge that it is more remarkable than the normal solutions for the lessening of the environment. In the composition, there are a couple of examinations showing the effect of the saline application on environment rise, regardless of what may be generally anticipated, others exhibit that utilization of saline response for the rotational system to cartilage interface during osteotomy don't decrease the environment during the osteotomy to any immense degree. In the makers' data, this is the essential examination revolves around the effect of the water framework

environment to decrease warm climb. At the same time, it is surveyed in this examination that utilization of saline game plan is convincing or not for the diminishing of the warm mischief.

CONCLUSION

In the momentum assessment we surveyed the models similarly as new cartilage advancement, presence of pollution, debasement and fibrosis Our examination showed gigantic differentiation regarding the rot regards between control gathering (without water framework) and the social affair immersed with 25°C and 4°C saline. Defilement was not found in second and third get-togethers. At any rate bounteous saline water framework was significant for cleaning the action zone from any extras of the drill. It is felt that this can be a touch of space for wound patching.

In this assessment, it is made sure that the usage of saline water framework isn't just important to diminish environment climb on the cartilage during osteotomy, yet what's more convincing for cleaning the osteotomy site from any hard remnants.

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